

Techno-Economic Analysis of Hybrid systems with PEM Fuel Cell

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This paper presents a forklift hybrid system using PEM fuel cells and a battery as power source. In the first part the basic characteristics and the working energy principle of fuel cell technology are presented. Then different types of hybrid drive trains used in forklift trucks are described. In the last part, the feasibility of using hydrogen-powered PEMFC fuel cells as an alternative energy source for the drive train of forklift trucks is evaluated from a technical and economic point of view. The total cost of ownership of both technologies is compared to determine the economic costs or benefits associated with each technology. Shorter refueling time and constant power output has reduced idle time and increased productivity, ultimately impacting the productivity related costs in such a way that the fuel cell option has better financial results than battery powered forklift trucks.

Figure 1: Fuel cell powered forklift at HySA Systems.

Figure 2: PEM Fuel cell BOP

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